

nextGEMS

Next Generation Earth Modelling Systems

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About this document

This report describes the revisions to the land-surface information in the IFS and provides a first estimate on the importance of the representation of detailed surface heterogeneity in storm-resolving simulations.

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1 Executive summary

The land surface description in the ECMWF IFS up to cycle 2 was based on datasets produced in the early 2000's. These input datasets do not fully benefit from the developments of remote sensing land cover and vegetation data sets during the past 20 years. The latest generation of remote sensing products of land cover and vegetation have higher spatial resolution, in the order of 1 km and finer, and improved classification algorithms. Therefore, to take full advantage of the recent advances in earth observations and demonstrate the capacity of storm-resolving models in capturing landscape variability globally, the IFS land surface information was revised. This revision aimed at improving the representation of land-surface heterogeneities at storm-resolving resolutions, enabling a first assessment of the importance of resolving the full scales of surface heterogeneity for global climate statistics.

The IFS land cover and vegetation information was revised for the cycle 3 simulations using the latest ESA-CCI land cover and Copernicus Global Land Service Leaf Area Index datasets. In addition to the high resolution land information (300m resolution, while the previous dataset used had 1 km resolution) the key differences include (i) the reduction of high vegetation cover, which is compensated by an increase of low vegetation; (ii) introduction of a realistic disaggregation of LAI between low and high vegetation types while conserving the original product seasonality and (iii) representation of urban conditions.

Land Surface Temperature (LST) is the primary focus in this report as it carries the blueprint of the surface energy budget, reflecting land conditions: (i) LST is the radiative surface temperature controlling the surface longwave radiation emission, (ii) the surface sensible heat flux depends on the gradient between near surface air temperature and LST; (iii) the surface latent heat flux depends on the gradient between near surface air humidity and saturated humidity assumed at the surface temperature; and (iv) the ground heat flux depends on the gradient between LST and the underlying soil temperature. We use the LST product from the Satellite Application Facility on Land Surface Analysis (LSA SAF) which provides clear-sky estimates of LST over the geostationary Meteosat Second Generation (MSG) region every 15 minutes since 2004 with a resolution of 3 km at the equator. Two examples illustrate that the high-resolution surface information as well as an urban scheme had a positive impact in cycle 3 IFS simulations, when compared with cycle 2 when evaluated against satellite LST, improving both the spatial and diurnal LST variability. A methodology for estimating the resolved sub-grid scale variability of LST was developed and showed consistent results between the cycle 3 simulations and the satellite data, particularly in (i) showing the added value of IFS 4.4km versus IFS 9km in representing the sub-grid scale LST variability and (ii) differences between daily maximum and minimum LST variability and their relation with the underlying orography variability, highlighting the role of high resolution land cover surface heterogeneities in controlling LST variability. The inclusion of ICON cycle 3 simulations in the report also showed some limitations in representing LST, particularly with the underestimation of maximum temperatures. These are associated with the current model approach to close the surface energy balance within the uppermost soil layer with finite thickness and heat capacity. This report demonstrates the capacity of storm-resolving simulations in representing land-surface heterogeneities, verified against satellite observations. These developments are necessary in the context of the increasing need for local climate information, and for local projections of direct socio-economic relevance.

2 Project objectives

The following table lists the overall objectives of nextGEMS. Objectives that the current report contributes to are flagged with yes.

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
O1	
To develop two SR-ESMs for applications	
(i) by demonstrating their capacity to more realistically represent the coupled (land-ocean-atmosphere) climate system, also through an ability to better leverage observations;	yes
(ii) by performing the first global multi-decadal (30 y) SR-ESM based climate projections, testing for out-of-sample climate trajectories, i.e., surprises, and thereby giving a new perspective on uncertainty; and	no
(iii) by expanding their scope to begin more physically coupling 'Earth-system' processes, including the carbon cycle and the atmospheric aerosol	no
O2	
To use SR-ESMs to test emerging and long-standing hypotheses underpinning our understanding of climate change:	
(i) that convective organization contributes importantly to Earth's energy budget and the strength of cloud feedbacks;	no
(ii) that a more explicit representation of cloud-aerosol interactions mutes aerosol-radiative forcing;	no
(iii) that 2 km to 200 km scale atmospheric and oceanic circulations are of leading order importance for air-sea fluxes in the tropics, thereby influencing not only the mean tropical and mid-latitude climate, but also its variability, including extremes;	no

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
(iv) that storm-scale variability in weather systems and of the land surface strongly influence extra-tropical climate and extremes, for instance by conditioning circulation regimes, like blocking;	no
(v) that capturing landscape variability globally greatly improves the realism with which regional climate can be simulated; and	yes
(vi) that storm-scale variability through its impact on hydrological extremes affects the carbon budget, with associated implications for the global carbon (emissions) stock-take.	no

O3

To build new, more integrated, communities of ESM users by:

- | | |
|--|----|
| (i) exploiting the necessity of developing SR-ESMs around a centralized infrastructure to create development and analysis paradigms that can more directly involve a broader and more distributed scientific community; and | no |
| (ii) by exploiting the affinity between what people experience and what SR-ESMs simulate (i.e., events, in addition to statistics) to more directly involve non-scientific users in model development, thereby fostering Knowledge Coproduction. | no |

This deliverable directly contributes to the achievement of specific objectives indicated in the description of the Work Package:

Objectives of WP8	Relevance in this deliverable?
Evaluate surface energy, water and momentum balance components as well as near-surface meteorology over land at storm-resolving resolution against observations and coarser resolution simulations (O1)	yes

Objectives of WP8	Relevance in this deliverable?
Represent land-surface heterogeneities at storm-resolving resolution by making use of the latest generation remote sensing products of land cover and vegetation (O1)	yes
Prepare the NextGEMS models to best serve the science and applications, by implementing online output statistics co-developed with stakeholders, with a pilot project focusing on solar energy (O1 and O3)	no
Expand scope of the SR-ESM by coupling it offline to a terrestrial biosphere model (O1)	no

3 Detailed report on the deliverable

3.1 Introduction

The land surface description in the ECMWF IFS up to cycle 2 was based on datasets produced in the early 2000's. These input datasets do not fully benefit from the developments of remote sensing land cover and vegetation data sets during the past 20 years. The latest generation of remote sensing products of land cover and vegetation have higher spatial resolution, in the order of 1 km and finer, and improved classification algorithms. Therefore, to take full advantage of the recent advances in earth observations and demonstrate the capacity of storm-resolving models in capturing landscape variability globally, the IFS land surface information was revised. This revision aimed at improving the representation of land-surface heterogeneities at storm-resolving resolutions, enabling a first assessment of the importance of resolving the full scales of surface heterogeneity for global climate statistics.

Land surface temperature (LST) temporal and spatial variability carries a blueprint of the surface energy budget. The temporal variability of LST is mostly dominated by the diurnal cycle of available energy, modulated by cloud presence, and synoptic variability. Averaged over a few weeks, LST filters the cloud and synoptic variability, remaining the diurnal cycle. On these time-scales, the daily maximum of LST spatial variability will be mostly dominated by the land surface conditions (e.g. elevation, land cover, vegetation state, soil moisture state, etc.). Therefore, the LST spatial variability of the daily maximum should reflect the different sources of land surface variability, making it an optimal candidate for evaluating the realism of storm-resolving models in representing such surface heterogeneities. LST is also one of the few land surface variables that can be directly derived from satellite data, and there are several available datasets which provide high quality and long data records. In this report, satellite LST is used to assess the impact of the revised land information in IFS from cycle 2 to cycle 3 as well as to explore the realism of the nextGEMS storm resolving models from a land surface perspective.

3.2 Land surface in the IFS

3.2.1 Overview of land surface representation in IFS

The land-surface scheme in the IFS ECLand supports a wide range of global weather, climate and environmental applications. ECLand is a flexible system created to facilitate modular extensions in support of NWP and society-relevant operational services (Boussetta et al., 2021). ECLand computes the surface energy and water fluxes, as well as the evolution of soil temperature, moisture, and snowpack. The surface-atmosphere exchanges take place in a surface skin layer separating the sub-soil from the lower troposphere. The skin layer has no heat capacity, and its temperature is used to compute the upwelling longwave radiation, making it directly comparable with satellite LST. Each grid-box can represent different types of land cover using multiple tiles, including bare ground, dominant high vegetation type, dominant low vegetation type, intercepted water (on the canopy), and shaded and exposed snow.

In the IFS version used in nextGEMS up to cycle 2 and in current operations at ECMWF, the vegetation cover is derived from the Global Land Cover Characteristics dataset (GLCC, Loveland et al., 2000) and the Leaf Area Index (LAI) is based on a 2000-2008 climatology derived from Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) collection 5 data and rescaled using a static LAI dataset to guarantee neutral impact on the ECMWF model (Boussetta et al., 2012). These input datasets do not fully benefit from the developments of remote sensing land cover and vegetation data sets during the past 20 years. Recent studies have identified limitations of the current land cover and LAI datasets used in ECLand and proposed several updates (Johannsen et al., 2019; Nogueira et al., 2020; Nogueira et al., 2021). However these updates were not available in cycle 2 simulations nor tested in high resolution global simulations. In the following section the datasets used and their processing are presented.

In addition to the revised land cover and vegetation, cycle 3 IFS simulations also include two other revised components at the surface: (i) land water mask and (ii) an urban scheme. The new land-water mask uses newly generated glacier data and a new land-water and lake fraction mask. The lakes are also benefiting from updated lake depth data. The main data sources for land-water mask are from the Joint Research Centre (JRC) with nominal resolution 30 m. The high resolution information at 30 m is used in the data merge and aggregated to 1 km (area conserving aggregation transforming binary information at 30 m to fractional information at 1 km). The urban scheme considers the urban environment as an interface connecting the sub-surface soil and the atmosphere above (McNorton et al., 2021). The urban tile comprises both a canyon and roof fraction. In terms of energy and moisture storage, the uppermost soil layer is not specific to the tile but represents a grid-cell average. This results in a weighted average that accounts for both urban and non-urban environments. The albedo and emissivity values used in radiation exchange computations are determined based on an assumption of an infinite canyon, taking into account shadowing effects. The roughness length for momentum and heat varies according to urban morphology, and snow clearing and runoff are also represented via simplified assumptions.

3.2.2 IFS Land cover and vegetation revision

Land cover

The land cover revision for the IFS (i.e., vegetation types and fractional coverage) was based on the ESA-CCI dataset. This dataset provides consistent maps of land cover, based on the 22 classes from the land cover classification system developed by the United Nations Food and Agriculture Organization. The latter are derived by combining remotely sensed surface reflectance and in situ observations. The dataset is available at the 300 m spatial resolution, on an annual basis since 1992 (Copernicus Climate Change Service, 2019).

The land cover data processing included (i) the spatial aggregation from the original 300 m and (ii) the transformation of the ESA-CCI land cover classes to the IFS land cover types. The 300 m spatial resolution ESA-CCI land cover grid points are spatially aggregated to the target model resolution by counting the number of 300 m pixels of each class occurring within each grid-cell of the target grid. This step creates maps of fraction cover for each ESA-CCI land cover type at

the target grid. These fractional covers of ESA-CCI classes are then converted into the IFS land cover classes using a cross-walking table. The latter identifies, for each of the ESA-CCI class the fraction of IFS and cover type. Finally, the new IFS land cover types fractions are processed to compute the fractional cover of low and high vegetation, as well as the dominant types of low and high vegetation attributed to each grid point.

Vegetation

The LAI was obtained from the Copernicus Global Land Service (CGLS) version 2 at 1 km resolution, covering the entire globe. The LAI product is derived from the SPOT-VEGETATION and PROBA-V satellite observations using the algorithm described by Verger et al. (2014).

The total LAI data is processed in 3 steps:

1. A climatology for the period 2010-2019 was computed at the original resolution of 1 km.
2. The LAI climatology is aggregated to the target grid and disaggregated into low and high vegetation.
3. The disaggregation of low/high LAI is further processed for consistency with the land cover map and to conserve the total LAI.

For the spatial aggregation and the low/high disaggregation, each 1 km pixel of CGLS LAI is aggregated to the target grid total LAI (lai), while the low and high LAI (lai_{lv} , lai_{hv}) are derived considering the low vegetation fraction (cvl), high vegetation fraction (cvh), and land sea mask (lsm). A further processing is applied to reinforce land cover consistency and to guarantee total LAI conservation. The low and high vegetation LAI for each vegetation type are scaled to guarantee consistency in terms of annual maximum. For each vegetation type and grid-point, the maximum annual LAI is computed, and the median of the distribution is taken as representative for that vegetation type LAI. A new LAI is then computed by scaling the maximum LAI in each grid-cell by that median value, weighted by the vegetation fraction. Finally, the updated (lai_{lv} and lai_{hv}) for each calendar month is scaled to conserve the total LAI with a multiplicative factor, limited between 0.2 and 5 to avoid large unrealistic corrections. These processing steps guarantee the conservation of the total LAI from the original satellite product as well as a consistent processing for any model resolution, similarly to the land cover data processing.

IFS cycle 3 updated land cover and vegetation

As previously described, the revised land cover based on the ESA-CCI products for IFS cycle 3 includes the update of the low and high vegetation types and cover. The revised high vegetation types do not include the types “interrupted forest” and “mixed forest”, which were mostly replaced by deciduous broadleaf trees. Additionally, the revised low vegetation types do not include the “semi-desert” type, which was replaced in most regions by shrubs. Despite these changes, the main dominant vegetation patterns remain similar. The largest changes came from the vegetation cover, which is shown in Fig. 1, in terms of effective vegetation cover. In

the IFS, the fraction of the vegetated tiles (effective vegetation) is computed as the product of the input vegetation cover by the vegetation density, which is given as a look-up table for each vegetation type (see Table 8.1 in Chapter 8 ECMWF, 2023). In the revised land cover, there is a general reduction of high vegetation (Fig. 1 b), which is replaced by low vegetation (Fig. 1 a) and bare-ground (Fig. 1 c). There is also a decrease in the bare ground cover in some semi-arid regions (e.g. Rocky mountains, East Australia), which is associated with the removal of the “semi-desert” type, which had a low vegetation density. Resuming, there are two key differences in the IFS cycle 3 revised land cover: (i) the removal of two types of high vegetation, which include “interrupted forest” and “mixed forest”; and (ii) the reduction of high vegetation cover, which is compensated by an increase of low vegetation.

Figure 1: Differences between cycle 3 and cycle 2 IFS effective low vegetation cover (a), effective high vegetation cover (b), and effective bare ground cover (c).

The revised LAI based on the CGLS dataset has a higher annual amplitude, when compared with the previous climatology used. This behavior is exemplified in Fig. 2 for the Iberian Peninsula. In the previous climatology there was almost no seasonal cycle with LAI being nearly constant around 2 for both low and high vegetation types (black solid lines). The revised LAI shows a stronger seasonality (red lines) as well as differences between low and high vegetation types (compare panel a and b of Fig. 2). The LAI disaggregation and rescaling procedure produces the expected behavior of higher LAI for high vegetation, when compared with low vegetation, and guarantees the conservation of the total LAI given by input satellite data (Fig. 2 c).

3.3 Results

In this section the results are organized in two topics: (i) examples of local/regional scale of the impact of the IFS land revision and (ii) a preliminary analysis focusing on the assessment of the

Figure 2: Mean annual cycle of LAI (m^2m^{-2}) for low vegetation (a), high vegetation (b), and total LAI (c), averaged over the Iberian Peninsula. These figures compare the cycle 2 LAI (black curves) with the new revised LAI in cycle 3 (solid red lines). The total original LAI (dotted magenta in c), the intermediate LAI aggregation (red dotted red lines), and an independent dataset based on MODIS data (blue lines) are also included.

realism of the storm-resolving simulations from a LST perspective.

LST is the primary focus due to its blueprint of the surface energy budget reflecting land conditions. We use the LST product from the Satellite Application Facility on Land Surface Analysis (LSA SAF) which provides clear-sky estimates of LST over the geostationary Meteosat Second Generation (MSG) region every 15 minutes since 2004 with a resolution of 3 km at the equator (Trigo et al., 2008). For consistency with the model simulations, a 5-year period was taken between 2018-2022 and the mean diurnal cycle was computed for each season for all years. The same methodology was applied to the model simulations, considering only clear-sky conditions in each model simulation, to generate a dataset which is comparable with the satellite observations. In the case of IFS, total cloud cover below 0.3 was used for the clear-sky screening (Johannsen et al., 2019). For ICON, the vertically integrated sum of cloud ice and water below 0.005 was used for the filtering of the clear-sky conditions.

3.3.1 Local and regional scales

This section presents two examples of local/regional scale of the impact of the IFS land information revision, including the comparison between cycle 2 and cycle 3 simulations.

Between cycles 2 and 3, significant improvements have been achieved in representing urban heat island effects around the globe at the km-scale in IFS (Fig. 3). To give an example, the difference in the LST diurnal cycle between the city of Warsaw and its more rural surroundings during the 5-year clear-sky hours (in the JJA season) depicts a clear urban heat island effect (Fig. 3a), with temperature anomalies compared to the rural areas in excess of typically 1 K over any given hour of the day, and exceeding 2 K around noon. When compared with the LSA SAF satellite product, the results in cycle 3 show a closer fit to the satellite product than was possible in cycle 2; both the average temperature difference over the day, as well as its temporal variability, is better captured (Fig. 3a). Although the sub-diurnal variability is qualitatively well represented, the cycle 3 modeled urban-rural contrast is systematically around 0.5 K smaller than observations. This could be due to missing anthropogenic heating, as well as an

underestimation of the urban heat storage due to too low urban cover or building height. The scatter plots comparing the LSA SAF with cycle 2 and cycle 3 LST difference between the city and the rural surroundings, colored by local time, further highlight the improvements from cycle 2 to cycle 3 which are quantified in Fig. 3b-c.

In terms of spatial variability of LST JJA-mean clear-sky anomalies, cycle 3 simulation (year 2020) matches the km-scale details of the LSA SAF dataset (2018-2022) well (compare Fig. 4, a and b), while cycle 2 IFS did not provide such local detail in the absence of updated land use/land cover maps plus urban scheme (Fig. 4, c). Note also that cycle 3 partially reduced the warm areas in cycle 2 in the South and East of Warsaw, which can be partially attributed to the land cover and vegetation revision in cycle 3.

The second example in this section is focused over a region from Paris to South Switzerland. The JJA daily minimum LST anomaly over the region is shown in Fig. 5 for IFS and ICON in cycle 2 and cycle 3 and for the reference satellite LSA SAF (panel e). The LST anomaly is computed by removing the field mean and highlights two spatial signals with positive LST anomalies: (i) Paris urban heat Island and (ii) Swiss lakes Geneva and Neuchâtel as well as lake Constance. During nighttime the LST differences between the Paris region and the surroundings are not as high as during daytime, as seen in the previous results in Warsaw, but it is still possible to clearly identify the urban heat island effect in the LSA SAF data. The lake temperature signal is much more clear with a pronounced warm anomaly induced by the water thermal inertia. In cycle 2 IFS shows the lakes signal but misses Paris, while ICON misses both. In cycle 3 simulations, IFS partially captures the warm anomaly in the Paris region, and ICON also identifies the warm lake temperatures much more clearly. While ICON does not have yet a detailed description for urban conditions, in cycle 3 it benefited from the introduction of a revised high resolution lake cover mask enhancing the model capability to represent the spatial patterns of LST induced by lakes.

The two examples presented in this section illustrate clearly that high-resolution surface information as well as an urban scheme had a positive impact in cycle 3 simulations, when compared with cycle 2 when evaluated against satellite LST. Moreover, these developments are necessary in the context of the increasing need for local climate information on a city scale, and for local projections of direct socio-economic relevance.

3.3.2 Realism of high resolution

This section presents a preliminary analysis focusing on the assessment of the realism of the storm-resolving simulations from a LST perspective, including only cycle 3 simulations. For this purpose, the LST daily maximum and minimum fields (derived from the mean diurnal cycle) at each model native resolution and the satellite product, were spatially aggregated to a regular 0.25x0.25 grid, by considering all the grid-points inside each coarse grid cell, and the standard deviation was computed to estimate the sub-grid scale variability of LST. This coarse resolution was selected as it is the same as the ECMWF ERA5 reanalysis (Hersbach et al., 2020) and close to the resolution of the climate models that participated in the High Resolution Model Inter-comparison Project (HighResMIP) in CMIP6 (Haarsma et al., 2016). Since these estimates are produced for clear-sky conditions, all pixels with less than 10% of available data (high frequency

Figure 3: Top panel (a) mean diurnal cycle of land surface temperature (LST) difference between the city of Warsaw and its rural surroundings, for the summer months (JJA) during clear-sky conditions. The cycle 3 IFS 4.4km simulation is given with blue line and cycle 2 in orange, while observations from LSA SAF are given in black. Bottom panels: one-to-one scatter plot of urban heat island intensity for Warsaw, with LSA SAF observations on the X axis and IFS simulations on the Y axis. The shown simulations are cycle 3 IFS-FESOM 4.4km (b), and cycle 2 IFS-FESOM 4.4km (c). Each dot represents the 5-year clear sky summer mean at the given local hour for one pixel within the Warsaw urban area.

of cloudy conditions) were excluded to guarantee a robust sampling.

Figure 4: Maps of Land Surface Temperature temperature difference with respect to the rural reference for LSA SAF (a), cycle 3 IFS-FESOM 4.4km (b), IFS-FESOM 4.4km cycle 2(c) at 12 00 Local Time. The displayed values are a 5-year summer clear-sky average.

We start the analysis with an evaluation of the models performance in terms of their mean spatial variability of LST. Figure 6 compares the daily LST maximum and minimum for JJA for the entire MSG disk between the model simulations and LSA SAF. Both IFS simulations at 4.4km and 9km show very similar results and an overall good agreement with the LSA SAF for both daily maximum and minimum. Although the scatter plots show a good 1:1 relation, there is some spread which is associated with regional differences between the models and LSA SAF. ICON simulations have a large cold bias (-7.66 K) of the daily maximum, and the bias is larger for higher temperatures. This underestimation of daily maximum in ICON can be primarily attributed to high thermal inertia since the model does not have a skin layer (Heidkamp et al., 2018).

The results in Fig. 7 show the estimated sub-grid scale variability of LST in a grid of 0.25x0.25 in cycle 3 IFS and ICON simulations along with the estimates from the LSA SAF product. It is possible to identify three main regions with higher variability: (i) regions around the Mediterranean basin; (ii) eastern Brazil and (iii) south central Africa. These regions are characterized by a variety of land surface heterogeneities such as topography and land cover. There is a general agreement between the model simulation and the satellite estimates except in the case of ICON that tends to underestimate the variability in western Brazil and south central Africa.

The density scatter plots comparing the model's simulations of the resolved sub-grid scale LST variability with the LSA SAF satellite estimates (Fig. 8) show that the slope of a linear regression between the satellite estimates and the model simulations are the following: IFS 4.4 km: 0.82, IFS 9km: 0.67, and ICON: 0.59. These results show the added value of the higher resolution in IFS 4.4km simulations, when compared with IFS 9km, with an enhancement of the representation of land surface heterogeneities and their impact on LST spatial variability. The underestimation of ICON in western Brazil and central south Africa requires further investiga-

Figure 5: Maps of the anomaly of daily minimum LST (K) for the JJA season. In each map, the anomaly is computed by removing the mean over the region. The left panels show the IFS-FESOM 4.4km in cycle 2 (a) and cycle 3 (c) while the right panels are for ICON in cycle 2 (b) and cycle 3 (d). The satellite LSA SAF is represented in panel (e). In the maps two regions are highlighted: Paris surroundings (top left) and South West Switzerland including lakes Geneva and Neuchâtel.

tion, but is likely associated with the previously identified underestimation of LST, particularly in high temperature conditions, associated with a high thermal inertia of the skin temperature in ICON.

To further understand the sub-grid scale variability of LST, we compared it to the underlying sub-grid scale variability of the orography in Fig. 9 for the three model simulations and LSA SAF and for both daily maximum and minimum LST. In the figures we overlay the expected LST sub-grid scale variability associated with a gaussian orography distribution assuming that LST varies like air temperature with a lapse rate of $9.8 K km^{-1}$ (dry adiabatic lapse rate) and $4 K km^{-1}$. If the LST variability would fall within these limits, it could be explained only by the orography variability. Considering the LSA SAF distribution in Fig. 9 a,e we find a clear difference between the daily minimum and maximum, with the later showing a much higher variability. These results show that LST spatial variability is higher during daytime due to the surface heterogeneity response to the available energy. Both IFS simulations (at 4.4 km and 9 km) show a similar behavior for the daily maximum when compared with the satellite observations. For the daily minimum, the IFS (and ICON) tend to fall mostly within the expected LST variability due

Figure 6: Density scatter plots of the simulations LST JJA mean diurnal maximum (top) and minimum (bottom) versus LSA SAF for IFS 4.4km (a,d) IFS 9km (b,e), ICON (c,f) for the MSG domain (see Fig. 7).

to orography, missing some spatial variability in regions with low orography variability. This is also the case for ICON in the daily maximum.

The results in this section were also repeated with data from the MSG in the Indian Ocean satellite, which is also produced by LSA SAF, and extends the spatial coverage to 110° East (including India and Himalaya). The results are qualitatively similar, although with more variability which could be due to the quality of the satellite data, since this region is covered by an older MSG satellite. Future efforts, extending this analysis to the full globe would benefit from georing LST product. Although these results are not global (-60° West to 60° East and extended to 110° East with MSG Indian Ocean), our findings are expected to be globally representative. The proposed methodology for estimating the resolved sub-grid scale variability of LST showed consistent results between the cycle 3 simulations and the satellite data, particularly in (i) showing the added value of IFS 4.4km versus IFS 9km in representing the sub-grid scale LST variability and (ii) differences between daily maximum and minimum LST variability and their relation with the underlying orography variability, highlighting the role of high resolution land cover surface heterogeneities in controlling LST variability.

3.4 Conclusions

This report presents the revision of the IFS land surface information with state-of-the art land cover and vegetation high resolution datasets to demonstrate the capacity of storm-resolving

Figure 7: LST mean diurnal cycle maximum (June-August) sub-grid scale variability in cycle 3 IFS 4.4km (a), IFS 9km (b), ICON (c) and LSA SAF (d). Gray areas over land denote missing data due to high frequency of cloudy conditions (above 90%).

Figure 8: Density scatter plots of IFS 4.4km (a) IFS 9km (b) and ICON (c) LST mean diurnal cycle maximum (June-August) sub-grid scale variability versus LSA SAF for the entire MSG domain (see Fig. 7).

simulations in representing land-surface heterogeneities. The key impacts in the IFS cycle 3 revised land cover include: (i) the removal of two types of high vegetation, which include “interrupted forest” and “mixed forest”; (ii) the reduction of high vegetation cover, which is com-

Figure 9: Density scatter plots of LST JJA mean diurnal maximum (top) and minimum (bottom) sub-grid scale variability as function of the orography sub-grid scale variability for LSA SAF (a,e) IFS 4.4km (b,f) IFS 9km (c,g), ICON (d,h) for the MSG domain (see Fig. 7). The two dashed black lines in each panel represent the expected LST sub-grid scale variability associated with a gaussian orography distribution with a lapse rate of 9.8 K km^{-1} (dry adiabatic lapse rate) and 4 K km^{-1} .

compensated by an increase of low vegetation and (iii) the representation of urban conditions. The LAI disaggregation and rescaling procedure produces the expected behavior of higher LAI for high vegetation, when compared with low vegetation, a consistent seasonal evolution of the two vegetation components, and guarantees the conservation of the total LAI given by input satellite data. Two examples presented in this report illustrate clearly that high-resolution surface information as well as an urban scheme had a positive impact in cycle 3 simulations, when compared with cycle 2 when evaluated against satellite LST. The proposed methodology for estimating the resolved sub-grid scale variability of LST showed consistent results between the cycle 3 simulations and the satellite data, particularly in (i) showing the added value of IFS 4.4km versus IFS 9km in representing the sub-grid scale LST variability and (ii) differences between daily maximum and minimum LST variability and their relation with the underlying orography variability, highlighting the role of high resolution land cover surface heterogeneities in controlling LST variability. ICON cycle 3 simulations were also included in the evaluation showing an underestimation of the daily maximum temperature, particularly for high temperatures as well as an underestimation of the sub-grid scale variability of LST. This is likely associated with a high thermal inertia associated with the current model approach to close the surface energy balance within the uppermost soil layer with finite thickness and heat capacity.

4 References (Bibliography)

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5 Dissemination and uptake

5.1 Uptake by the targeted audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is:

x	The general public (PU)
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This reports is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

5.2 This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience

This document will be freely available to the general public from the project website (<https://nextgems-h2020.eu>). Part of the results will be presented at EGU 2024 (EGU24-8254 “Demonstrating the potential of km-scale multi-annual coupled global simulations in nextGEMS: a (urban) surface perspective” by Xabier Pedruzo-Bagazgoitia et al.)

6 Deliverable timeliness

Is the deliverable delayed?

no

7 Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

Not applicable.

8 Sustainability

Links built with other deliverables, WPs, and synergies created with other projects

The work presented in this deliverable contributes to the work in WP9, particularly task 9.2 (Day and warm spells) and WP3 by evaluating the configurations of the SR-ESM for the production simulations. This work also strengthened the synergies with the EUMETSAT Satellite Application Facility on Land Surface Analysis (LSA SAF) project (<https://lsa-saf.eumetsat.int>), showing the value of high resolution satellite products from LSA SAF in evaluating SR-ESM.

9 Full track of dissemination activities

- Cycle 1 Hackathon 19. – 22. October 2021 in Berlin
- "Science meets Art" - NextCalendArt 2022
- Office Hour with IBERDROLA on solar energy in January 2022
- UCM Student Hackathon, 01. – 03. April 2022 near Madrid
- Cycle 2 Hackathon 26. June – 02. July 2022 in Vienna
- Storms & Ocean summer slackathon 31. June – 06. July 2022 at the Bornö Institute for ocean and climate studies, Sweden
- "Science meets Art" - NextCalendArt 2023
- Mini-hackathon of Storms & Land at Wageningen University 04. – 06. April 2023
- Cycle 3 Hackathon 29. May – 02. June 2023 in Madrid
- "Science meets Art" - NextCalendArt 2024

10 Full track of publications and IP

Publications within the project can be found on our website: <https://nextgems-h2020.eu/publications/>